

D4.3

Report on specification, development and provision of the Blockchain functionality and smart contracts (final report)

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Abstract

This deliverable presents all the updates and evolution related to the blockchain-based components implemented in DAFNE+ Platform and described in D4.1.

The document reports the improvements of all the DAFNE+ Platform blockchain components, including the core concepts, the architectures, the main functionalities, and the technical specifications.

Keywords

Blockchain, Non-Fungible Tokens (NFTs), Marketplace, Revenue Models, Web3

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Table of contents

1	Executive summary.....	9
2	Introduction.....	11
2.1	Purpose and context of the document.....	11
2.2	Document structure.....	11
2.3	Dependencies to-from other WPs.....	11
3	Blockchain Realm.....	13
3.1	Infrastructure and Networks.....	15
3.2	New Smart Contracts and features.....	18
3.2.1	DAFNE+ NFT Governance.....	19
3.2.2	DaoDafne.....	22
3.3	NFT Tool - Updates.....	23
4	NFT Marketplace.....	26
4.1	Updates on Architecture, specifications and interfaces.....	26
4.2	New functionalities.....	34
4.2.1	User experience enhancing features.....	35
4.2.2	Core marketplace features.....	37
4.2.3	System and integrations.....	42
5	DAO System.....	43
5.1	Description.....	43

5.2	Main features.....	44
5.3	Architecture and technical specifications.....	47
5.3.1	Architecture.....	47
5.3.2	Specifications.....	49
5.3.3	GUI section.....	54
6	Conclusion.....	66
7	References.....	67

List of figures

Figure 1: Blockchain Realm Architecture v2.....	14
Figure 2: Mumbay to Amoy Switching.....	16
Figure 3: Polygon Amoy Faucet.....	18
Figure 4: Dafne+ DAO Governance Framework.....	19
Figure 5: DAFNE+ NFT Governance.....	21
Figure 6 - Workflow add proposal realm.....	23
Figure 7: NFT Marketplace Architecture.....	26
Figure 8: New Marketplace UI.....	35
Figure 9: 3d Models visualisation.....	36
Figure 10: Moderation System.....	38
Figure 11: Multi-item Cart.....	41
Figure 12 - Dao Architecture.....	48
Figure 13 - Access Workflow.....	50
Figure 14 - Create Proposal Workflow.....	52
Figure 15 - Vote Workflow.....	53
Figure 16 - Home Page (Not Connected).....	55
Figure 17 - Home Page (Connected).....	56
Figure 18 - Create a New Proposal Action.....	57
Figure 19 - New Proposal 1/2.....	58

Figure 20 - New Proposal 2/2.....	59
Figure 21 - Proposal List.....	60
Figure 22 - Vote Proposal.....	61
Figure 23 - Create transaction (with MetaMask).....	62
Figure 24 - MetaMask Detail.....	62
Figure 25 - Enter to Proposal Detail.....	63
Figure 26 - Proposal detail.....	64
Figure 27 - Proposal Expired.....	65

List of tables

Table 1: Cost comparison.....	25
Table 2: NFT Marketplace interfaces.....	27
Table 3: List of badges.....	39

Abbreviations

API	Application Programming Interface
DAO	Decentralized Autonomous Organisation
NFT	Non-Fungible Token
UI	User Interface
UX	User Experience
PoS	Proof of Stake
GUI	Graphic User Interface
WP	Work Package

1 Executive summary

The Blockchain technology is a core part of the DAFNE+ Platform and all the main functionalities for the management of Digital Assets (including NFT creation) are based on it.

The first version of the DAFNE+ Platform included three blockchain-based applications: The Blockchain Realm, the NFT tool and the Marketplace.

The Blockchain Realm consists of a blockchain-ready framework able to:

- make simple and fast interactions with the blockchain networks (Polygon and Ethereum)
- facilitate the deployment and integration of Smart Contracts
- provide APIs with core blockchain features (NFTs, Tokens, Smart Contracts methods, Monitoring, etc.)

The NFT tool, is a dedicated component for facilitating the creation, management, and sale of NFTs within the DAFNE+ Platform and together with the DAFNE+ NFT Marketplace it plays the crucial role of allowing the NFT creators to publish and monetize their artistic productions.

The NFT Marketplace is essentially a virtual place where digital artists and creators can advertise and sell their work, while being remunerated fairly.

The first version of DAFNE+ Platform and its blockchain components were described in D4.1. These components were tested and evaluated in several workshops and with end-users in order to collect useful feedback for refining and improving the core functionalities, during the first phase of the project.

This document presents the updated version of the blockchain-based tools, leveraged on the first round of feedback collected and reported in D5.1 and D2.3.

In addition, new functionalities based on Smart Contracts were already planned to be implemented in a later stage of the project, such as the DAO System and the related mechanisms.

D4.3 - Report on specification, development and provision of the Blockchain functionality and smart contracts (final report)

This phase of the project, that has an important milestone with a new release of the DAFNE+ Platform in September 2024, improves and consolidates the Blockchain Realms and all the blockchain related features.

Some minor upgrade, mostly on the DAO system, will be implemented in the final stage of the project and reported in D4.4.

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2 Introduction

2.1 Purpose and context of the document

This document reports on the activities carried out under tasks T4.1, T4.2 and T4.3 in the second period of the project.

The main goal of this document is to describe the updates and the evolution of the blockchain-based applications for the DAFNE+ Platform: The Blockchain Realm, the NFT tool and the Marketplace.

In addition, it reports the new Smart Contracts implemented in the Blockchain Realm as well as the new DAO System, that will be part of the second version of the DAFNE+ Platform.

2.2 Document structure

In addition to the Executive Summary and this introductory chapter, the document is structured into 4 additional chapters:

- Chapter 3 provides a summary of the Blockchain Realm component, focusing on the important updates and the new functionalities implemented.
- Chapter 4 describes the maturation and evolution of the NFT Marketplace, including the updates on the architecture, the new functionalities and interfaces.
- Chapter 5 introduces the concept of the DAFNE+ DAO and describes the implementation of the DAO System, including the smart contracts related functionalities as well as the frontend part that will be integrated in the next version of the DAFNE+ Platform.
- Chapter 6 concludes this document.

2.3 Dependencies to-from other WPs

Tasks T4.1, T4.2, and T4.3 considered all the use cases, requirements and scenarios defined in WP2 and the DAFNE+ Architecture as reference for the implementation of the components.

In particular D2.1, D2.2 and D2.3 were used for the identification of requirements, as well as for the refinement phase, based on the feedback collected in the first validation phase.

D4.3 – Report on specification, development and provision of the Blockchain functionality and smart contracts (final report)

The output of these document is important for T4.5, in which the overall DAFNE+ Platform will be integrated and released as well as the WP5, where these components and blockchain features will be tested and evaluated within different scenarios in the next validation phase of the project.

3 Blockchain Realm

As described in D4.1, the Blockchain Realm is the core components within the DAFNE+ Platform in charge of managing and implementing the Blockchain features and integrating the blockchain infrastructures and networks.

Compared to the first version of the DAFNE+ Platform, the main update related to the Blockchain Realm was the implementation and integration of new Smart Contracts for the DAO System Management.

Figure 1 below shows the new version of high-level architecture of the Blockchain Realm, including the integration with DAO System.

FIGURE 1: BLOCKCHAIN REALM ARCHITECTURE V2

Already existing Smart Contracts and tools were also updated, accordingly to the feedback collected in the first validation phase as well as new features expected for the final version of the platform. These updates mainly involved the NFT tool.

Finally, another important update related to the Blockchain Realm was the Polygon Network switch from Mumbai to Amoy.

All the updates related to the Blockchain Realm are described in the paragraphs below.

3.1 Infrastructure and Networks

The Blockchain Realm main goal is to provide an interface between the DAFNE+ ecosystem and blockchain infrastructure.

Following the requirements elicited in D2.1 and as described in D4.1, in the DAFNE+ context two different Blockchains were integrated: Ethereum and Polygon.

In the first version of the DAFNE+ Platform two specific testnet have been supported: Sepolia (Ethereum) and Mumbai (Polygon).

During the first phase of the project, an important change was necessary for updating the Polygon testnet. In fact, in April 2024 the Ethereum Goerli Network (L1 network root for Mumbai) was deprecated and the main PoS testnet for Ethereum became Sepolia [1].

Many testnet networks are now available linked to Ethereum Sepolia, and among these, Amoy Network was selected for implementing DAFNE+ Polygon services.

FIGURE 2: MUMBAI TO AMOY SWITCHING

The deprecation affected DAFNE+ functionalities and moreover the contents and NFT already created within Mumbai Network.

In order to ensure the continuity of the DAFNE+ Platform a specific feature for migrating any existing content from Mumbai to Amoy was implemented both in the Content Management and NFT Marketplace.

Below the specifications of the Amoy Network:

Polygon Testnet - Amoy

Network Name: Polygon Amoy Testnet

New RPC URL: <https://rpc-amoy.polygon.technology/>

Chain ID: 80002

Currency Symbol: MATIC

Block Explorer URL: <https://amoy.polygonscan.com/>

Migrating to Amoy has brought an important benefit to DAFNE+ platform. In fact, the platform is now operating in a test environment that more closely matches the conditions of the Polygon mainnet. This allowed us to conduct more thorough testing and better anticipate issues that may arise in a production environment.

On the other side, an important challenge was encountered on the Amoy testnet related to token collection through Faucet.

In particular, in order to obtain test tokens, which is essential for the operation of our applications in the test environment, the new version of the Blockchain Realm uses a faucet accessible at <https://faucet.polygon.technology/>.

This faucet represents a significant improvement over the previous version, introducing more robust security measures. In particular, using a Discord account for authentication adds a layer of identity verification that helps prevent abuse and ensures a fairer distribution of test tokens.

FIGURE 3: POLYGON AMOY FAUCET

However the standard procedure for obtaining tokens through this faucet is to top up 0.2 MATIC at a time and, given the nature of our project, which requires a high number of transactions for content creation and management, this amount proved insufficient for our intensive testing needs.

In order to address this issue, a specific request to Polygon Faucet for requesting a larger amount of MATIC tokens has been done. The DAFNE+ Platform received now 100 MATIC, an amount that will allow to support the volume of transactions necessary for our tests until the end of the project.

3.2 New Smart Contracts and features

3.2.1 DAFNE+ NFT Governance

The minimum requirement for the implementation of a DAO Framework, as described in D2.3, is the possibility to define the DAO Governance mechanisms.

For the implementation of DAFNE+ DAO Governance, a specific framework has been designed. This framework, described in the Figure 4 below, allows any user registered within the DAFNE+ Platform to participate in the management of the platform itself.

FIGURE 4: DAFNE+ DAO GOVERNANCE FRAMEWORK

In order to certify the registration of the users to the DAFNE+ Platform and make them eligible for creating and voting proposal, a specific governance NFT has been defined and implemented.

Since the DAFNE+ Platform Governance is available for each user registered, to participate in the decisions of the community as a DAFNE+ Member, the NFT was implemented using a particular token: the Soulbound NFT.

Soulbound tokens (SBT) [2] are an innovation in blockchain and cryptocurrency that are designed to be non-transferable once they have been assigned to a specific address. This makes them particularly useful for purposes such as governance and voting within a DAO (Decentralized Autonomous Organisation).

Soulbound tokens can be used to verify the identity of DAO members, ensuring that each address represents a unique and recognized participant.

Since Soulbound tokens cannot be transferred, the risk of buying and selling of voting rights is eliminated, maintaining the integrity of the voting process. This ensures that only legitimate and active members can participate in decisions.

In summary, Soulbound tokens can significantly improve governance and voting processes in DAOs, providing greater security, integrity, and recognition of member reputation.

Within the Blockchain Realm a specific Soulbound NFT was created. This NFT is assigned to each user registered to the DAFNE+ Platform in an automated way.

The Governance NFT implements specific mechanisms for the NFT assignment as well as for the identification of the user. Its main functions are displayed in Figure 5.


```
contracts > NftGovernance.sol
1 // SPDX-License-Identifier: MIT
2 pragma solidity ^0.8.0;
3
4 import "@openzeppelin/contracts/token/ERC721/ERC721.sol";
5 import "@openzeppelin/contracts/access/Ownable.sol";
6
7 contract NftGovernance is ERC721, Ownable {
8     uint256 private _tokenIdCounter;
9     mapping(address => bool) private _hasSoulboundToken;
10    mapping(address => uint256) private _tokenCreationDates;
11
12    constructor() ERC721("NftGovernance", "SBT") {}
13
14    function connectToDAO(address to) public {
15        require(!_hasSoulboundToken[to], "Already has a soulbound token");
16        _mintSoulboundToken(to);
17    }
18
19    function _mintSoulboundToken(address to) internal {
20        uint256 tokenId = _tokenIdCounter;
21        _tokenIdCounter += 1;
22
23        _mint(to, tokenId);
24
25        _hasSoulboundToken[to] = true;
26        _tokenCreationDates[to] = block.timestamp;
27    }
28
29    function _transfer(address /*from*/, address /*to*/, uint256 /*tokenId*/) internal virtual override {
30        require(false, "SoulboundToken: non-transferable token");
31    }
32
33    function hasSoulboundToken(address addr) public view returns (bool hasToken, uint256 creationDate) {
34        hasToken = _hasSoulboundToken[addr];
35        creationDate = _tokenCreationDates[addr];
36    }
37 }
38
```

FIGURE 5: DAFNE+ NFT GOVERNANCE

connectToDAO

The function takes an address to parameter and checks if the given address already has a Soulbound token. If the address does not have a Soulbound token, it calls mintSoulboundToken(to) to issue a new token.

_mintSoulboundToken

This function issues a new token for the given address and updates the `_hasSoulboundToken` mapping.

`_transfer` function

This function makes tokens non-transferable as before.

`hasSoulboundToken`

This function checks if a given address already has a Soulbound token.

3.2.2 DaoDafne

DaoDafne is the smart contract that fully manages the DAO. It is invoked both to create a new proposal and to vote on a pre-existing proposal. In both cases it performs an insertion on the blockchain of a record with all the necessary information collected by the front end but only the insertion of a new proposal is invoked by Blockchain Realm, because the voting function, is launched by the user through its MetaMask web 3 wallet.

DaoDafne consists of two main functionalities:

- `addProposal` (Blockchain Realm)
- `vote` (Web 3 wallet MetaMask)

As guessed by the name `addProposal` performs a write-in to insert a new proposal. `Vote` on the other hand performs a write corresponding to a vote for an existing proposal.

The data that make up a proposal and must be passed are as follows:

Title, Description Start date, End Date, Quorum, Threshold, Discussion link, Image, Number of options and detail of options (see add proposal workflow in Figure 6).

FIGURE 6 - WORKFLOW ADD PROPOSAL REALM

Insights into the functionality and workflow of all these operations are detailed in 5.3.2 - Specifications “Create a new Proposal”.

3.3 NFT Tool - Updates

The NFT Tool of the DAFNE+ platform is responsible for the handling of the NFTs and the blockchain interactions necessary to the functionalities of the marketplace. The first version of the tool included a list of basic features, such as the minting and buying of NFTs, and is reported in D4.1.

The updates of the NFT Tool have focused on enhancing the offered features and functionalities to comply with the modern technology standards in the field of Web3, as well as enabling cost efficiency and making the DAFNE+ NFT service more easily accessible and usable. The present subsection outlines the new features developed under the NFT Tool.

- **Migration to Amoy:** as already described in the previous chapters, DAFNE+ operates using two different blockchain networks; Ethereum and Polygon. In the first version, to support Polygon the Mumbai testnet was employed. Due to major upgrades, Ethereum decided to deprecate Goerli and so Polygon deprecated the Mumbai network, introducing a new one in January 2024. The new network is Amoy and is based on the Sepolia testnet. The deprecation affected DAFNE+ as the services had to migrate to a new network as well. The NFT Tool is designed with flexibility and adaptability in mind, as blockchain is an ever-changing field of upgrades and improvements. It was reconfigured to support the new network for minting new content and added a feature to give the ability to NFT owners to migrate their NFTs on the new network.
- **Updates on the NFT Smart Contract structure for cost efficiency:** To reduce the gas related costs the new NFTs minting process needed to be updated. The first version focused on providing the functionality in a basic yet robust form, while the present version focuses on efficiency. The NFT Smart Contract business logic was updated, while still complying with the ERC-1155 standard, it now provides the ability to manage multiple different NFTs under the same contract, affecting the NFT minting flow. In the previous version, new NFT translated to a new contract being deployed, affecting the cost of the transaction. The update means that the minting of NFT translates only to consuming a function of a smart contract. The update therefore leads to lower gas fees as well as more environmentally friendly and sustainable interactions with the marketplace. Indicatively, you can find the comparison in computational cost in minting an NFT in the Sepolia testnet with the previous version and the new version in the table below.

TABLE 1: COST COMPARISON

	Previous Version	New Version	Comparison
Gas consumption	3,100,650	237,121	92.36% decrease
Transaction fee (Applying a base fee of 20,924800495 Gwei and MaxPriorityFee of 1.5 Gwei)	~69531457 Gwei	~5317 Gwei	99.99% decrease
Cost in € (For the Ether price of 2224€)	154.62 €	0.01183 €	99.99% decrease

- Enabling cart functionality:** To lower the costs even further and improve the experience of the users in the platform, allowing them to interact with the marketplace in a familiar format of the off-chain marketplaces, a new feature is included that enables the buying of different NFTs under the same transaction. The feature is implemented in the NFT Smart Contract of the tool, an extension of the previous feature.
- NFT Royalties:** To empower creators and provide further motives for the usage of the platform, the NFT Smart Contract is compliant with the ERC-2981 standard that allows creators to apply NFT Royalties. Upon minting an NFT they can define a percentage that will be returned to the original creator from the resells of their NFTs.
- Transaction history of NFTs:** To enhance transparency about the operations taking place, the NFT Tool now provides additional details about the transaction history of NFTs as well as new ways to track the details of the transaction using popular block scanning platforms, such as Etherscan for Ethereum.

4 NFT Marketplace

4.1 Updates on Architecture, specifications and interfaces

The architecture of the NFT Marketplace at its core has remained unchanged. However, updates have been implemented through integrations with other DAFNE+ services to provide an enhanced experience to the users. Details about the complete list of new features added are reported in section 4.2. An overview of the architecture of the marketplace with its subcomponent, the NFT Tool, and the integrated services is provided in the Figure 7 below.

FIGURE 7: NFT MARKETPLACE ARCHITECTURE

A part of the updated interface of the marketplace is provided in the table below:

TABLE 2: NFT MARKETPLACE INTERFACES

NFT Marketplace		
Interfaces	badge/	
	Description	The interface allows the handling of the badges in the DAFNE+ marketplace. It covers functionalities related to the definition, retrieval, editing and deletion of badges.
	Protocol(s) used	HTTPS
	Methods	POST, GET, PUT, PATCH, DELETE
	Message	POST/PUT/PATCH: <pre>{ "name": string", "description": ""string", "value": 0, "metric_field": "string", "metric_model_content_type": "string",</pre>

		<pre> "award_model_content_type": "string", "condition_type": "string", "icon": image } GET: { "id": 0 "name": string, "description": ""string", "value": 0, "metric_field": "string", "metric_model_content_type": "string", "award_model_content_type": "string", "condition_type": "string", "icon": image, "created_at": timestamp }</pre>
--	--	--

nft/	
Description	This endpoint handles the creation, editing and deletion of NFT, object on the side of the backend service.
Protocol(s) used	HTTPS
Methods	POST, GET, PUT, PATCH, DELETE
Message	<p>POST/PUT/PATCH:</p> <pre>{ "name": "string", "description": "string", "value": 0, "metric_field": "string", "metric_model_content_type": 0, "award_model_content_type": 0, "condition_type": "energetic", "icon": "string" }</pre> <p>GET:</p> <pre>[{</pre>

		<pre> "id": 0, "name": "string", "description": "string", "value": 0, "metric_field": "string", "metric_model_content_type": 0, "award_model_content_type": 0, "condition_type": "energetic", "icon": "string", "created_at": "2024-08-08T13:08:19.748Z" }] </pre>
	marketplace-item/	
	Description	This interface exposes functionality related to the handling of items on the marketplace.
	Protocol(s) used	HTTPS

	Methods	POST, GET, PUT, PATCH, DELETE
	Message	<p>POST/PUT/PATCH:</p> <pre> { "name": "string", "description": "string", "type": "image", "owner": 0, "tags": [], "external_link": "string", "display_image": "string", "nft": 0, "source": 0, "unlockable_content": "string", "work_title": "string", "work_version": "string", "composer": "string", "composer_page": "string", "presentation_ur": "string", "public_work_excerpt": "string", "display_video": "string", "downloads": 0, } </pre>

		<p>GET:</p> <pre>[{ "id": 0, "name": "string", "description": "string", "type": "image", "owner": 0, "tags": [], "external_link": "string", "created": "2023-10-12T13:17:07.658Z", "modified": "2023-10-12T13:17:07.658Z", "views": 0, "display_image": "string", "source": "string", "source_media": "string", "nft": 0, "unlockable_content": true, "unlockable_content": "string", "work_title": "string", "work_version": "string",</pre>
--	--	---

		<pre>"composer": "string", "composer_page": "string", "presentation_ur": "string", "public_work_excerpt": "string", "display_video": "string", "downloads": 0, "chainid": 0, "badges": [{ "id": 0, "name": "string", "description": "string", "value": 0, "metric_field": "string", "metric_model_content_type": 0, "award_model_content_type": 0, "condition_type": "energetic", "icon": "string", "created_at": "2024-08- 08T13:01:58.276Z" }]</pre>
--	--	--

		<pre>], "overall_rating": 0 }]</pre>
--	--	---

The complete API of the marketplace can be found deployed in the production environment of DAFNE+ under this link: <https://dafneplus.eng.it:7009/api/schema/swagger-ui/>.

4.2 New functionalities

The updates on the marketplace focus on providing an elevated and intuitive user experience, increasing the accessibility of the service to a wider group of users, independent of the background and technological savviness. Additionally, the toolset offered by the marketplace has been expanded with new features that aim to empower creators further, enrich the content offered, give more opportunities for dissemination and attracting a wider audience. The new functionalities and be grouped in the following categories:

- User experience enhancing features
- Core marketplace features
- System integration features

Provided below are images displaying the new version of the marketplace incorporating new features that are described in detail in the following subsections.

FIGURE 8: NEW MARKETPLACE UI

4.2.1 User experience enhancing features

- **Interactive display for 3D Models:** To provide a dynamic and immersive experience and engage users with the distributed product of 3D model types, a new feature was implemented that allows the rotation, zooming and examining of 3D models from various angles. The interactive functionality enhances the model visualisation offering a more comprehensive understanding of the item's details and characteristics. By leveraging rendering technologies, the interactive display ensures high-quality

and responsive interactions, significantly improving the overall user experience and aiding in informed decision-making, as well as increasing the marketability of produced 3D model items.

FIGURE 9: 3D MODELS VISUALISATION

- **Pins explaining complex terms:** To ensure the engagement of non-technical users in the marketplace and increase its accessibility, the marketplace now provides explanations of complex terms through pins that the users can hover to learn more information about the details required or provided.

- **Remembering filtering options of users:** To provide a tailored experience based on users' interests the marketplace remembers the users' last applied filtering options, so next time they login they are greeted with items they are truly interested in. This feature was requested by Use-Case 2.
- **Automatic wallet configuration:** In the new version of the marketplace the users are unloaded of the burden of configuring their Web3 wallet with the appropriate blockchain networks beforehand. After selecting their network of choice in the NFT creation form, if they don't have it set-up already, MetaMask extension pops up asking them to add this network to their wallet. The removal of the extra step of configuration is expected to increase the onboarding of users unfamiliar with blockchain technology.
- **Markdown enabled asset descriptions:** To allow the appropriate description of marketplace items, especially for items related to software and repositories, where users are familiar with README.md structures, the description field is updated with Markdown enabled. So, users can enrich their descriptions exactly as they would in Git repositories systems such as GitHub or GitLab. Formatting of code, headings, emojis and tables are now supported, with the ability to edit asset descriptions after the listing of items on the marketplace.
- **Revamped UI/UX:** A revision of the marketplace design and the overall experience has been performed, with feedback originating from experts within the consortium partners which led to the redesign of the UI of the marketplace main pages. The new design is modern and dynamic, yet simplistic enough to highlight the important information and features. The users should find an even more intuitive experience navigating the marketplace.

4.2.2 Core marketplace features

- **Moderation system:** A new feature for the management and moderation of the content of the marketplace has been introduced, along with new roles on an administrative level. Users have the

ability to report items violating the community rules of DAFNE+, providing a reason for reporting. Administrators with the role of moderators have access to a page for managing user reports. They are provided of all the reports received grouped by marketplace items. They are informed about the user reporting, the reason for reporting, the time received and the status of the report. When a report is first received, moderators have the ability to either ignore the report in case they consider that it does not violate the rules and ethics of DAFNE+, or they can trigger a warning. In that case the owner of the item is informed about the report and is called to action within a specific period of time, while the item is temporarily hidden from the marketplace landing page. Failure to provide a solution to the report will give the ability to the moderator to permanently remove the item from the marketplace.

FIGURE 10: MODERATION SYSTEM

- **Reputation system:** DAFNE+ marketplace now offers a reputation system in the form of badges. Marketplace items that satisfy certain conditions are awarded with the appropriate badge which aims

to drive the promotion of quality content on the platform, reward creators and provide aid NFT collectors and buyers to their search of content. For example, marketplace items that are “liked” over five times are awarded the “Starred” badge. The reputation system is designed to be highly dynamic and flexible. So, it is possible to:

- a. Extend badges to user profiles as well. For example, users are awarded special badges on their portfolios for creating many items.
- b. Add new badges that can be defined based on any new type of information added on the marketplace.

For an initial iteration we have introduced a specific list of badges to the system that are outlined in Table 3. However, as enabled by design, the list can be easily expanded with minimal effort to accommodate any new badge definition.

TABLE 3: LIST OF BADGES

Badge Name	Badge description	Condition	Icon
Trending	Awarded to items that have received a high number of likes, showing they are highly appreciated by users.	The item exists in the wish list of more than 5 users.	
Loved	Awarded to items that have garnered a significant number of views, indicating they are currently in high	The item has been viewed more than 100 times.	

	demand and widely noticed by users.		
Hot Pick	Awarded to items that have been downloaded frequently, highlighting their popularity and desirability among users	The item has been downloaded more than 3 times.	
Best Seller	Awarded to items that have been purchased numerous times, marking them as top-selling and highly sought-after products	The item has been purchased more than 3 times.	

- Rating system:** DAFNE Adding to the features for enhanced integrity, providing incentives for supplying and creating quality content, and aiding the users in their browsing experience on the marketplace, a rating system has been implemented. Users can add 1-to-5-star ratings on marketplace items and be able to view the overall rating. They are able to rate an item only once, so that the rating system is unbiased and reflects the true opinion of the DAFNE+ creators and collectors.
- Cart functionality:** To lower the costs of transactions and provide a familiar online shopping experience to the users, DAFNE+ offers cart functionality allowing users to add multiple items and buy them while triggering only one transaction. This update is an extension of the new relevant feature developed

under the NFT Tool and it works. The feature is enabled only for buying items that are minted on the same chain.

FIGURE 11: MULTI-ITEM CART

- **Public view of the marketplace:** To attract more users, and enhance the discoverability of the DAFNE+ marketplace, unauthenticated users that do not belong to the DAFNE+ ecosystem can get a glimpse of the marketplace and items with capabilities being restricted to only viewing the pages and content.
- **Enhanced support for work repositories:** New fields have been added to items of type “Work Repository” related to Use Case 2. The new fields are aiming to better support the specific group of

users for the advertisement and the discoverability of that content and are compliant with the format of platforms they are familiar with such as IRCAM’s multimedia library of work collections.

4.2.3 System and integrations

- **Sharing on LinkedIn:** The marketplace is integrated with the LinkedIn API Tool that was developed under T4.4 and reported in D4.2. This integration gives the option to users to share marketplace items on their LinkedIn pages, opening new streams for advertising their DAFNE+ created content.
- **Recommendation Engine Integration:** Another step for providing a tailored experience to the users is the integration with the recommendation engine developed under WP3. The recommendation engine is provided with user activity from the marketplace such as the content they have saved to their wish list, and the content they have created and bought in order to provide recommendations of content they might be interested in. On the marketplace landing page the users can now enable the “For You” option to be displayed with content that applies to their interests and needs.
- **Full integration with Content Management:** Users can now create marketplace items directly from the content management system or they can select the content management items to list to the marketplace from the item creation form. This integration provides a smooth experience in the user’s journey to the DAFNE+ platform when creating content.
- **Migration to Amoy:** As described in section 3. as well, the DAFNE+ marketplace has now migrated from Mumbai to Amoy. In the marketplace, items that were minted in the Mumbai network are displayed but disabled and carry the “Deprecated” flag. Item creators and owners were informed about the change and can log in to the marketplace and migrate their items to the Amoy network.

5 DAO System

5.1 Description

As already described in D2.1 and in the DAFNE+ Architecture, the DAO tool is one of the Applications of the DAFNE+ Platform.

A Decentralized Autonomous Organisation (DAO) is an organisation governed through smart contracts on a blockchain network. These smart contracts encode the rules and decision-making processes, allowing participants to vote freely and eliminating the need for traditional forms of centralized governance. The DAFNE+ Platform is designed to support the creation and management of DAOs, providing a robust infrastructure for decentralized decision-making.

Within the DAFNE+ ecosystem, users will be able to participate in a variety of key actions essential to the functioning of a DAO. These include voting on proposals, initiating new proposals, and allocating funds. All these actions will be accessible through a user-friendly DAO interface, which ensures that users can interact with the DAO seamlessly. The platform leverages blockchain technology to ensure that all transactions and decisions are transparent, immutable, and secure.

The integration of the DAFNE+ Blockchain Realm will further enhance the management of DAOs by incorporating specific smart contracts that govern various aspects of DAO operations. These smart contracts will automate processes, enforce rules, and facilitate trustless interactions among participants, reducing the potential for human error or manipulation.

Given that the DAO section is a blockchain-based application, user authentication will be handled through integration with Web3 wallets. This integration is crucial for ensuring that users can securely access and interact with the DAO. The Web3 wallet connection, provided by the overall DAFNE+ platform, will enable users to authenticate their identity, sign transactions, and manage their digital assets seamlessly. This ensures a

secure and efficient user experience, allowing participants to fully leverage the benefits of decentralized governance without compromising on security.

Overall, the DAO section of DAFNE+ Platform contributes to an effort that aims to support the management of organisations operate by enabling the creation and management of DAOs. By providing a comprehensive set of tools and integrations, DAFNE+ empowers users to engage in decentralized governance, fostering a more transparent, democratic, and efficient organisational structure.

5.2 Main features

The DAO System within the DAFNE+ platform is designed to provide a comprehensive suite of features that enable users to effectively engage in decentralized governance. The following are the main features that define the DAO of DAFNE+:

Decentralized Voting System:

The platform supports a robust voting system in which participants can cast their votes on various proposals. Each member of the DAFNE+ platform is entitled to vote, in equal measure. This is guaranteed by a Non-transferable NFT (“Soulbound”) assigned to each member, upon first access to DAO, ensuring fair and proportional representation.

The voting process is transparent and tamper-proof, protected by blockchain technology, ensuring that all votes are recorded immutably and can be checked at any time.

Proposal Management

Users can create and submit proposals for new initiatives, changes in governance, or allocation of funds.

Proposals go through a defined life cycle, including submission, discussion, voting and implementation stages, ensuring a structured and democratic decision-making process.

In the first release it is possible to choose between 2 types of proposals: “Governance” and “Treasury” depending on the topics covered, as specified in D2.3 - Use Case Specifications:

- Governance (DAO rules) Fee value
Voting mechanism (+ Emergency)
Quorum & Thresholds values
- Treasury New tech features – exp Propose to change the DAO model
New initiatives/ideas
Crisis Management - Super Admins

The users will have the possibility to initiate a proposal either using the Discord dedicated channels or directly in the DAFNE+ platform.

Smart Contract Integration

The DAO is powered by smart contracts that automate governance processes. These contracts ensure that rules and decisions are enforced without the need for intermediaries.

Web3 Wallet Integration

User authentication and signing of voting transactions are handled through the MetaMask Web3 wallet integration. This feature allows users to securely connect their wallets to the DAFNE+ platform, ensures that users have control over their digital assets and that all interactions with DAO are secure.

User-Friendly Interface

The DAO interface is designed to be intuitive and accessible, facilitating user participation in governance activities.

This interface provides clear information about proposals, voting options, and voting results, enabling users to make informed decisions beforehand and analyze results afterwards.

Transparency and Auditability

All actions within the DAO are recorded on the blockchain, providing a transparent and verifiable record of decisions and transactions. This transparency creates trust among participants, as they can verify the integrity of the governance process.

Automated Compliance

The platform includes features to ensure compliance with relevant regulations and standards. Smart contracts are built to automatically enforce compliance rules, reducing the risk of legal problems.

Community Engagement Tools

The DAO includes tools to promote community engagement and collaboration. Users can discuss proposals, share ideas, and provide feedback through integrated communication channels.

Community engagement features help build a strong, active and collaborative DAO community.

These features make DAO DAFNE+ a powerful tool for decentralized governance, providing a secure, transparent and efficient way for organisations to manage their operations democratically.

5.3 Architecture and technical specifications

5.3.1 Architecture

DAO System has been implemented as a sub-app of the DAFNE+ Platform, using the micro frontend architecture approach described in D4.2.

The DAO system consists of a three-layer architecture as shown in Figure 12.

FIGURE 12 – DAO ARCHITECTURE

UI Layer (sub-app-dao-management), includes a web interface that allows DAFNE+ users to participate in the DAO, creating proposals or voting on existing proposals. This Layer was implemented using REACT framework [3] and represents the entry points for the users. All the main features implemented within the tool are available through specific sections in the User Interface.

Service Layer (server-dao-management), provides business logic, including Proposal entry capabilities, proposal voting, integration with Blockchain Realm. This layer was implemented using NodeJS [4] and Nest.Js [5] and is integrated with the Identity Manager for managing the authentication and the authorisation mechanisms of the DAFNE+ Platform.

Storage Layer (Mongo DB) provides data management of proposals, votes and users entitled to vote. This layer includes a NoSQL database (MongoDB) [6] for storing application data.

5.3.2 Specifications

Login and NFT Governance

After login, by making an entry into the DAO tool, an initial check is made to see if the “user - account MetaMask” pair has an associated governance NFT. This NFT is required to access the DAO features and is assigned to all registered users of the DAFNE+ platform when they make an initial access to the DAO. This functionality provides that a user can add proposals of any type (Governance or Treasury) and can vote on proposals that are created after his first entry, the one in which he is associated with an NFT. Thus, a proposal can only be voted on by users who are already censored and who have associated a Governance NFT at the time the proposal is created (Figure 13).

FIGURE 13 - ACCESS WORKFLOW

Create a new proposal

To create a new proposal, a whole set of data defining the proposal must be provided (Figure 14).

One must provide:

- Title
- Description
- Start date (from today onward, default today).
- End Date (from creation date onwards, default today + 1 month)

If today's date is earlier than the creation date, the status of the proposal is pending. This is a case that may occur if there is a need for discussion and confrontation by using the appropriate channels (discussion link) before opening the vote.

If today's date is between the creation and closing date, the status of the proposal is active, and the proposal can be voted on.

If today's date is after the closing date, the proposal is closed, and by entering the details you can see the voting results.

- Quorum (absolute/relative/simple).

Absolute: percentage relative to eligible voters, if greater than the specified percentage, the option wins.

Relative: percentage relative to votes cast if greater than the specified percentage, the option wins.

Simple; In simple there is no percentage; the option that collected the most votes wins.

- Threshold (the minimum number of votes to be collected for a proposal to have a winner).
- Discussion link (platform where there can be a forum for discussion of the various options, possibly even before the proposal becomes active).
- Image
- Number of options (min 2)

FIGURE 14 - CREATE PROPOSAL WORKFLOW

Once the proposal is created, it is placed on the blockchain (DaoDafne) and the number of the transaction submitted is returned. A blockchain entry has a cost that is borne by a system account. It should be noted that the price is borne by the DAFNE+ platform, not by the user who creates the proposal.

Vote on a proposal

To vote on a proposal, one must go into detail, and if the proposal is active, all possible options are presented. Only one choice can be made (multiple choice is not provided for the moment). A user can vote only once for

a proposal. Checking is done on the “User - Account” pair (changing accounts does not allow voting a second time).

Voting also creates a transaction on the blockchain where the vote is recorded via the DaoDafne smart contract. This time the cost of the transaction is charged to the user, via the MetaMask account with which they are connected to the platform (Figure 15).

FIGURE 15 – VOTE WORKFLOW

Expiration of a proposal

When a proposal concludes, a check is made on the votes collected, a check is made on whether the quorum specified at the creation stage was reached, and a check is made on whether the required threshold was passed. If all conditions are met, the option that has collected the most votes is declared the winner. This can be seen by going into the details of the proposal itself, where the evidence is shown. Clearly, if one of the required conditions is not met, it is specified that there is no winner for the proposal.

5.3.3 GUI section

Home

- Home page with welcome message, not connected with MetaMask (Figure 16)

FIGURE 16 - HOME PAGE (NOT CONNECTED)

- Home page with welcome message connected with MetaMask (Figure 17).

FIGURE 17 - HOME PAGE (CONNECTED)

Tab Dao - List Proposals

- The list of proposals outstanding in the platform is displayed. The detail can be reached by simply clicking the button “Details”.
- There is a button to add a “New proposal” (Figure 18).

FIGURE 18 - CREATE A NEW PROPOSAL ACTION

Add Proposal

- You are prompted to enter all the fields necessary to define the elevation. Eventually, pressing the appropriate ADD button will add it (Figure 19 and Figure 20).
- List of information required:
 - Title
 - Description
 - Start Date
 - End Date
 - Quorum (absolute/relative/simple)
 - Discord link (optional for any discussion of the proposal)

- Image
- Number of Options (min 2)

FIGURE 19 - NEW PROPOSAL 1/2

Start Date
02/08/2024 12:00

End Date
20/08/2024 13:00

Type
Treasury

Quorum ●
Relative 50%

Threshold
10

Discussion Link
<https://discord.com/treasury/987654321>

Image
Choose File No file chosen

Number of Options
2

Option 1
Yes ✕

Option 2
No ✕

+ Add

dafne+ Privacy Policy

FIGURE 20 - NEW PROPOSAL 2/2

Vote Proposal

- It is reached from the Home by clicking on the button “Details” of the proposal (Figure 21)

D4.3 – Report on specification, development and provision of the Blockchain functionality and smart contracts (final report)

FIGURE 21 - PROPOSAL LIST

- Each option is displayed in a button with the Label entered.
- There is a card with the results of the votes collected up to that moment (Figure 22).

D4.3 – Report on specification, development and provision of the Blockchain functionality and smart contracts (final report)

FIGURE 22 - VOTE PROPOSAL

- A MetaMask form opens where confirmation is requested to submit the (voting) transaction (Figure 23 and Figure 24).

FIGURE 23 - CREATE TRANSACTION (WITH METAMASK)

FIGURE 24 - METAMASK DETAIL

Proposal Voted (detail)

- It is reached from the Home by clicking on the button “Details” of the proposal (Figure 25).

FIGURE 25 - ENTER TO PROPOSAL DETAIL

- Same page with Options cards (Figure 26).
- Card on the right with details of the proposal results:
 - Total votes collected
 - Quorum type (absolute, relative or simple)
 - Status proposal (pending, active, closed depending on where today's date falls in relation to Start Date e End Date)

- Chart with vote results.

FIGURE 26 - PROPOSAL DETAIL

Proposal Expired

- Going into the details of a proposal in Closed state, the results of the vote can be observed (Figure 27).

D4.3 – Report on specification, development and provision of the Blockchain functionality and smart contracts (final report)

FIGURE 27 - PROPOSAL EXPIRED

6 Conclusion

The DAFNE+ Platform blockchain-based components and tools have been consolidated and improved, ready for being integrated in the next release of the DAFNE+ Platform.

In fact, starting from the first version of the tools and components and based on the User Requirements collected in D2.1 and feedback reported in D2.3, the Blockchain Realm, the NFT Marketplace and NFT tools have been refined, improved and released in a new consolidated version.

In addition, the Blockchain Realm has evolved in order to manage the NFT for Governance and related Smart Contracts for the DAO System.

The DAO System implements a DAO Governance Framework for implementing a complete workflow for the management of the DAFNE+ Platform in a fully decentralized way, exploiting the DAO concept a blockchain-based functionalities.

All these tools will be integrated in the next version of the DAFNE+ Platform, expected as an intermediate release in September 2024.

This intermediate release will be exploited for a second round of testing and validation within the three main use cases of the DAFNE+ project.

At the end of the second validation phase, possible improvements on the blockchain functionalities could be implemented, mainly focusing on the evolution of DAO System and new revenue models mechanisms. These improvements will be implemented and integrated in the final version of the platform and reported in D4.4 at the end of the project.

7 References

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- [2] <https://learncrypto.com/knowledge-base/basics/what-are-soulbound-tokens-sbt-explained>
- [3] <https://react.dev/>
- [4] <https://nodejs.org/en>
- [5] <https://nestjs.com/>
- [6] <https://www.mongodb.com/>

